

Evaluation of an assistive upper-limb exoskeleton for severely impaired patients

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Abstract—Recent literature analysis showed the need for upper-limb assistive devices suitable for patients affected by neuromuscular pathologies. This work presents a novel upper-limb robotic exoskeleton specifically designed for muscular dystrophy patients. The exoskeleton is a 4 degrees of freedom robotic device that supports movement at the shoulder and elbow. The system can be controlled by the user in the task-space by driving a joystick or by means of speech recognition. The device has been field-tested on 5 dystrophic patients with the goal of evaluating performances, comfort, safety and usability of the device during daily life activities. Quantitative results on upper-limb functional performances with and without the exoskeleton are presented showing beneficial effects. Usability of the device has been evaluated as good, suggesting promising future developments.

Index Terms—Upper-limb, Assistive Device, Exoskeleton, Neuromuscular, Muscular Dystrophy.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade noticeable effort has been devoted to the development of assistive devices to support severely disabled people in performing activities of daily living. Motorized wheelchairs and mechanical ventilators have drastically improved their quality and expectation of life, but still they strongly depend on caregivers because of their limited arm functionalities. Few assistive devices for upper-limb impairment are commercially available, but most of them are not suitable for the most compromised patients, when there is not a significant residual arm functionality. Within this scenario, the BRIDGE and EMPATIA@Lecco projects aim at the development of an assistive mechatronic solution to help patients affected by neuromuscular diseases, such as Muscular Dystrophy (MD), to contrast the everyday difficulties in performing activities of daily life, boosting their self-esteem and relieving their caregivers workload [1]. In this work a novel device for the assistance of the upper-limb is at first described, then the results of a field-test on real-users are presented.

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II. DEVICE

The presented assistive device consists of a wheelchair-mounted 4 Degrees-of-Freedom (DoFs) lightweight motorized exoskeleton provided with gearbox stepper motors coupled with optical encoders that actively control the motion of each degree of freedom of the exoskeleton. 3 DoFs are supported at shoulder level (i.e., abduction and adduction, flexion and extension, and humeral rotation), and 1 DoF is assisted at the elbow level (i.e., flexion and extension). The mechanical design aligns each joint of the exoskeleton with the physiological joint-axis of the human arm. Two interaction ports between the arm and the device are present at the upper-arm and at the forearm. A centralized control scheme is implemented to let the user directly control the position of his/her hand in the Cartesian space. It relies on a numerical Inverse Kinematics algorithm that continuously computes the joint configuration needed to track the desired hand position. The chosen method avoids singular configurations and limits the movement of the exoskeleton within a work-space that depends on subject's arm stiffness and retraction. The intention of the user to move the arm in a certain direction is detected by means of two different human-machine interfaces: i) joystick and ii) vocal control [2]. While the joystick is exploited to identify a non-discrete desired displacement from the current position, the vocal control relies on a speech recognition engine that detects hot-words for the motion of the robot along the 6 principal directions. This multi-modal approach will allow each user to select the most suitable solution depending on his/her residual capabilities (Fig. 1).

III. PROTOCOL

The exoskeleton has been field-tested on dystrophic patients with the goal of evaluating performances, comfort, safety and usability of the device during daily life activities. Participants were recruited from in-patients and out-patients services at *IRCCS E. Medea* and at the *Rehabilitation Institute Villa Beretta*. The clinical study have been approved by local Ethical Committees and by the Italian Ministry of Health. In order to

Fig. 1. System architecture and connections

quantitatively assess the upper limb function, the Performance of the Upper Limb (PUL) module [4] was used as primary outcome measure. The PUL module includes 22 items with an entry item to define the starting functional level and 21 items subdivided into shoulder level (4 items), elbow level (9 items) and distal (wrist and fingers) level (8 items). On the other side, the Abilhand questionnaire for neuromuscular patients [5] evaluated the self-perceived manual ability of the patient. Abilhand scores are expressed in logit, where lower negative values mean that actions are considered impossible to be performed, while positive values are obtained if the patient believed to accomplish items more easily. The clinical protocol included three days of testing:

- Day 1: The baseline evaluation of the patient's upper-limb motor functionality is performed without the assistive device through the PUL module and the Abilhand questionnaire.
- Day 2: Patients performed a task-oriented training session when they could try the different human-machine interfaces, get used to the exoskeleton and explore the Cartesian space in free-motion.
- Day 3: Upper-limb functionality is assessed with the exoskeleton through the PUL module and the Abilhand questionnaire and compared to the baseline. The usability of the device is evaluated during this session by means of the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire [6].

IV. RESULTS

With this contribution we present the preliminary results acquired on five male patients, ranging from 18 to 53 years (mean age of 31 years). Three of them are affected by Duchenne MD, while two by Limb-Girdle type 2 MD.

A. Upper-limb performances results

According to PUL module results shown in Table I, all the patients increased their upper-limb performances when wearing the exoskeleton, with a median improvement of 12 points (IQR = 4.25). Most of the beneficial effects of the exoskeleton were recorded at the elbow level, while minor improvements were found at the wrist and finger levels.

TABLE I
PUL, ABILHAND AND SUS SCORES OBTAINED BY PATIENTS WITH AND WITHOUT THE EXOSKELETON.

Patient ID	DAY 1 (Without exoskeleton)		DAY 3 (With exoskeleton)		
	PUL	Abilhand	PUL	Abilhand	SUS
P01	42	4.814	53	2.996	92.5
P02	17	-1.845	29	-0.983	75
P03	18	-1.845	29	-0.983	72.5
P04	4	-6.176	18	-1.398	87.5
P05	2	-2.644	21	-0.009	75

B. Self-perceived abilities results

The Abilhand questionnaire results show that all participants, except one, perceived their upper-limb functionality increased when using the exoskeleton with a median increase of 0.86 logit (IQR = 2.98). Patients perceived that, over 22 activities, 15 actions were "impossible" and 7 "difficult" to accomplish, but overall they improved their perceived abilities with respect to the scenario without the assistive device.

C. Usability results

Overall high usability was accomplished during the tests: participants indicated a median SUS score of 75 over 100 points (IQR = 14.38) suggesting an above average usability.

V. DISCUSSION

The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy and the perceived functional benefit of the presented exoskeletal assistive device. Preliminary results obtained on five neuromuscular patients are encouraging: upper-limb functional ability increased and all participants perceived the device as beneficial and useful. Good usability was found and all participants considered the device comfortable to be used. Four patients preferred the joystick interface since they are used to move their electric wheelchair with a similar system. Improvements on encumbrance and aesthetic aspects were suggested.

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